

Research Article

A Cross-Sectional Study on Waste Management Plan Awareness and Their Disposal in Hospitals by Staff of Nishtar Hospital, Multan.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Identify the knowledge and practices of healthcare personnel, including managers, doctors, nurses, health workers, and cleaning personnel, regarding hospital waste management.

Study Design: A study of cross sectional.

Place and Duration: The study was performed in Nishtar Hospital Multan from October 2014 to October 2015 for the period of 1 year.

Methodology: A total of 80 health workers were included with deliberate sampling technique including 8 managers, 30 doctors, 25 nurses, 5 health personnel, 26 cleaning personnel. The data were collected in a structured questionnaire for subsequent statistical analysis.

Results: 82.4% (n = 84) of health personnel who were aware of biomedical waste. There was a significant difference (p = 0.003) between the different indicators of hospital staff on biomedical waste, risks associated with sharp objects (p = 0.000), insufficient waste disposal (p = 0.000). 65.4% (n = 66) of health personnel were aware of the level of separation of hazardous and non-hazardous wastes. 65.7% (n = 65) and 80.8% (n = 80) were aware of the health care staff's awareness about the transport of health care waste.

Conclusion: Information on biomedical waste management was satisfactory in health care workers, but better among doctors, nurses and administrative staff, and less in health care and cleaning staff.

Keywords: Waste Management, Awareness, Health Care Staff, Hospital.

INTRODUCTION

Hospitals are important places for production of waste. All departments of the hospital produce waste and the general product is waste in different types; health, household and administrative waste. Sanitary waste contains infectious, chemical, over-the-counter pharmaceutical and radioactive products and sharp body. Medical waste is an increasing source of concern because it is a source of pollution and pollution, which can lead to

diseases and diseases through direct or indirect contact with soil pollution, groundwater, surface waters and air [1,2]. Due to the recent increase in the incidence of hepatitis B and Hepatitis C in our country, there has been a growing public interest in the management of medical care wastes, along with other environmental issues. In many health centers in Pakistan, hospital wastes are simply disposed of in municipal waste and disposed of in

a similar manner. This indiscriminate collection and removal from the middle Infectious / hazardous waste poses a serious threat to exposed people.

The main groups at risk are doctors, nurses, health workers and hospital care personnel, 4 patients, visitors, workers, etc. From the outset, it was known that hospitals were giving medicines to sick people, but the negative effects of the produced wastes were unknown. Surprisingly, until recently, not enough attention has been paid to the destruction of hospital waste. Many healthcare facilities in the world prefer to be burned before the final disposal of medical waste, because they have many advantages. However, the emphasis on medical waste processing is not sustainable in the long run. Waste is nothing more than to learn how to use our economy efficiently, and it would be advantageous to discover the sustainable ways of medical waste [3, 4].

Aslike in many other developing countries in Pakistan, the removal of infectious wastes is a growing problem and will worsen the situation if not constantly managed. The hospital waste management policy is a precondition for the early and early disposal of hospital wastes [5,6]. Recommendations for developing countries, in addition to minimizing treatment and disposal and promoting underground wells, when other options are available, participation in effective activities, waste management of wastes, separation of cuts from other forms of medical wastes, development of safe storage and handling procedures, provision of protective equipment.

Emphasizing the awareness of different names working in a hospital regarding medical care wastes that will facilitate policy development and improve the management of clinical wastes and may be useful for policy development and information responsible persons [7].

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate the awareness and practice of hospital

waste management for health personnel of Nishtar Hospital Multan. Instructional hospitals providing improved diagnostic and treatment facilities in both specialist areas. The study took place in three months from October 2014 until October 2015. A self-developed questionnaire was made in simple English, translated in Urdu, and the data were recorded for later statistical analysis. The study was approved by the ethics committee of Nishtar Hospital Multan, and written approval of each participant was obtained. It was taken into account that the confidentiality of the participants was maintained during and after the study. The hospital personnel, managers, doctors, nurses, money medical staff and cleaning staff were considered to be included in the study.

All health personnel with different names were included in the survey if they had been working in these hospitals for at least one year. The level of education of health personnel was different according to their assignments and independently, they played an important role in improving the appropriate waste management in medical care. The sample was taken on the deliberate sampling of 80 health officers, 30 doctors, 25 nurses, 5 medical staff, 26 cleaning staff and 8 administrative staff. The data were entered in the SPSS version 16.0 software and a statistical analysis was performed to know the healthcare personnel working in these hospitals to know and apply the hospital waste management equipment, color coding of hazardous and non-hazardous waste. Use of personal protective equipment, Separation grade, Storage, Transport and final disposal of sanitary wastes.

RESULTS

In this study, 96 health care workers, except for this staff (26 (26.7%), Administrative Staff (8.3%) and paramedic cleaning, nurses, 25 (27.1% , 63 (62.0%) were males, 38 (37.0%) were less than five years old and 65 (69.0% were female of the health personnel working in this hospital, 28 (31.0%).

FIGURE - 1: FREQUENCY OF DIFFERENT DESIGNATIONS OF HEALTH CARE STAFF (N=96)

(Fig. 1), managers and nurses being maximum staff biomedical waste 084 (82.5%) were more aware of the difference by doctors, medical officers and cleaning staff. (88.6%) and unsuitable waste disposal were aware of environmental hazards and identified 84 (82.4%) of the risks associated with scissors shown in table II.

TABLE - II: KNOWLEDGE OF DIFFERENT DESIGNATIONS OF HEALTH CARE STAFF ABOUT PRACTICES OF HEALTH CARE WASTE MANAGEMENT IN THEIR HOSPITALS (n=96)

	Designation					Chi square value	P-value
	Doctor (n=40)	Nurse (n=27)	Paramedical (n=5)	Sweeper (n=16)	Administration (n=8)		
Does your hospital have proper waste management team?							
yes	19	18	2	5	4	5.550	0.235**
No	21	9	3	11	4		
Is there proper planning for waste management?							
yes	14	4	2	7	3	5.144	0.273**
No	26	23	3	9	5		
Is there proper display of SOPs of waste collection and management at relevant places?							
yes	8	5	0	1	3	4.824	0.306**
No	32	22	5	15	5		

** In significant at 5% level of significance

TABLE - I: AWARENESS OF HEALTH CARE STAFF OF DIFFERENT DESIGNATIONS ABOUT BIO MEDICAL WASTE (n=96)

	Designation					Chi-square value	P-value
	Doctor (n=40)	Nurse (n=27)	Paramedical (n=5)	Sweeper (n=16)	Administration (n=8)		
Do you know what is biomedical waste?							
yes	37	26	4	11	4	15.918	0.003*
No	3	1	1	5	4		
Do you think its important to manage biomedical waste properly?							
yes	38	27	4	14	8	7.617	0.107**
No	1	0	1	2	0		
Do You think there are any hazards related to improper waste disposal?							
Yes	40	25	4	8	8	30.435	0.000*
No	0	0	0	0	0		
Don't Know	0	2	1	8	0		
Do you think waste including sharps has any health risk?							
yes	36	25	5	5	8	37.106	0.000*
No	0	0	0	2	0		
Do You think there are any environmental hazards of improper waste disposal?							
Yes	40	24	3	4	8	50.902	0.000*
No	0	1	0	1	0		
Dont Know	0	2	2	11	0		

* Significant at 5% level of significance

** In significant at 5% level of significance

Most staff were 51 (51.0%) in the hospital with no suitable waste management equipment or waste management 71% (68.9%) believes that there is enough planning for the second half of the year. No color code for hazardous and non-hazardous wastes according to the majority 79 (77.5%). There is no specific point for waste collection compared to 78 (75.9%). When asked about the practice of wearing protective clothing, 70 (68.6%) thought that it was not applied at the hospital. When it comes to the level of separation of non-hazardous wastes, there were 35 (34.7%) and then 35 (34.7%) of those who believed that the maximum number was 32 (31.7%) in the nursing room and then reported less in source 21 (20.8%) and 13 (12.9%). Compared to them, most nurses (66.6%) gave the idea that this was a maintenance station and most of the cleaning staff were not aware of the level (62.5%).

According to 72 healthcare personnel (70.6%) there was no space for waste storage area. The utmost attention to waste transport is believed to be a staffed vehicle, 50 (50.5%) in an open vehicle and 15 (15.2%) in a private vehicle. The wastes are removed from the open air by 62 (62.6%) and 18 (18.2%), which are eliminated by burning. (Table III).

TABLE - III: KNOWLEDGE OF DIFFERENT DESIGNATIONS OF HEALTH CARE STAFF ABOUT VARIOUS PRACTICES REGARDING MANAGEMENT OF HEALTH CARE WASTE (n=96)

	Designation					Chi square value	P-value
	Doctor (n=40)	Nurse (n=27)	Paramedical (n=5)	Sweeper (n=16)	Administration (n=8)		
Is there any color coding for hazardous and non hazardous waste?							
yes	12	6	1	2	3	2.711	0.607**
No	28	21	4	14	5		
Are there dedicated points in the hospital for collection of waste?							
yes	10	6	3	3	1	4.448	0.349**
No	30	21	2	13	7		
Do Waste handlers wear protective clothing?							
yes	13	7	2	6	2	1.000	0.91**
No	27	20	3	10	6		
Is there any proper storage room for waste?							
yes	13	10	2	2	3	3.392	0.495*
No	27	17	3	14	5		
At what level hazardous waste is segregated from non hazardous waste?							
Right at source	12	2	2	1	3	37.240	0.000*
Nursing station	11	18	2	0	1		
Just before disposal	4	1	0	5	1		
Don't know	13	5	1	10	3		
How the waste is transported?							
Dedicated Vehicle	8	1	1	1	3	16.085	0.041*
Open cart	16	15	3	13	2		
Don't Know	16	9	0	2	3		
How the waste is disposed?							
Open dumping	25	17	4	8	6	17.465	0.026*
Incineration	9	7	0	0	1		
Don't Know	4	3	1	8	1		

DISCUSSION: Inadequate waste disposal is a growing problem, especially in developing countries. This shows a lack of information about appropriate management in health care personnel. In a study of medical waste management in Yemen, hospital managers found little awareness of the risks of medical waste. The results of this study show that administrative staff and nurses are the most conscious and medical waste personnel. A study of standards and management of biological wastes in the Vivekananda poly-clinic in India found less awareness of proper handling of hospital wastes among medical authorities, doctors and paramedical personnel. 9 Doctors and

nurses had better knowledge in the 10 Bangalore hospitals than the rest of the healthcare staff. In another study on the management of biomedical waste in India, it was found that general awareness was highest among doctors, followed by paramedical workers and at least non-medical workers. The majority of medical workers have information about biomedical waste management that is appropriate for this work. In Nigeria hospitals, it has been found that there is no sanitary waste management guidance in line with the current study regarding sanitary waste management. In the area of health services waste management in the Southwest region, it has been

found that medical waste management is of little importance as there is no integrated approach to policy making at the highest level decision-making mechanism.

Our work shows the same results. In a study conducted at 10 hospitals on hospital waste disposal practices in India, a study very similar to this study found that there was no separation of polyethylene bag waste recommended in 15. Regarding hospital waste management in Pakistan's Karachi hospitals, discrimination has not been followed in almost all hospitals. Cars and bags with color codes for waste transport were not enough. The hospital staff kept the wastes at hand under waterproof gloves and face masks, and did not realize the potential hazard according to WHO rules. On the other hand, the team responsible for the collection of medical wastes at the South African Hospital used full personal protection equipment. In general, the separation of wastes in different colors in bags appears to be a minimum practice that has not been followed in previous studies and is also a worrying concern for the use of personal protective equipment in Pakistan and should be applied to all health care facilities. In the Alaysian AM study on clinical waste management, discrimination, transport, appropriate waste management and education and awareness programs for hospital personnel were not on a par with each other. According to the research done in Nigeria, hospitals were differentiated waste. In a hospital, it is reserved at the point of origin and allocated 13 in the temporary storage area. Systems for collection and management of sanitary wastes, including containers and waste bins for separated wastes, are generally in a bad situation in the southwestern region. The management of hospital waste requires that those directly or indirectly associated with the hospital environment be kept separate from health facilities and destroyed so as not to be a source of risk for their health.

In India, it was found that the transport of waste was sufficient in the urban areas, but not in rural health facilities. Wheeled vehicles were used to

transport waste to the temporary storage area at the South African Hospital from the production site. According to this study, waste is transported through an open car, which is not a good practice and there is a need to educate health personnel about their risks.

The doctors, nurses, paramedical staff, cleaning staff and administrative staff at the beginning of this study thought that the wastes were thrown out of an open garbage dump. About half of the housekeepers did not have knowledge about waste disposal in their hospitals. In a survey of the disposal of sanitary wastes in the Southeast region, it was found that the proportion of waste water was disposed of in municipal solid wastes along with the solid wastes, and that some of them were often disposed of in furnace wastes. Incineration plants are the best way to dispose of medical wastes as long as they are well designed and located at a significant distance from the residential area or the main hospital building. Our work revealed that this method was never accepted and that wastes were clearly thrown away; which can be a source of disturbance and can pose serious risks to the health of the community.

CONCLUSION: In this study, it was concluded that information on biomedical waste management was satisfactory in health personnel but better in doctors, nurses and administrative staff compared to each other and fewer paramedics and cleaning staff. As these workers regularly participate in the biomedical waste management and processing process, there is a constant need for relevant guidance training to protect and protect all health personnel, especially medical and cleaning workers themselves. Visitors to the community hospital. This work has helped to build databases, information and statistics on the collection, transport, processing and disposal of clinical waste.

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